

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE BASED ON ANIMATION APPROACH

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Abstract. This paper discusses teaching listening skills using modern methods. Also, easy ways to improve listening comprehension skills are given below.

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Introduction. Among the four skills that are important in learning any language, listening comprehension is the most important. In language teaching and learning, speaking and writing a language is usually considered a factor of primary language use. Listening and reading skills come second. One of the reasons for this may be the difficulty of mastering listening skills. However, after the spread of IT technology, listening and understanding have been made easier by using different materials in language classes.

In addition, it should be noted that most of the student's class time began to be devoted to listening. We began to be convinced of the importance of listening often. In the natural order of learning any language, listening began to take the leading place. Mastery of one skill alone is nothing everyone was convinced that he could not produce it. Teachers began to pay great attention to teaching their students not only to speak fluently but also to listen and understand.

To master and use a new language perfectly, it is necessary to form existing knowledge and learn all the necessary information based on language-receptive skills, especially listening and reading skills. In this regard, a language learning program has been created for the convenience of students. By the way, this program is structured, it shouldn't have any input tests, output, or output.

A foreign language today is not just a part of the culture of a particular nation, but it is also the key to success, the future successful career of students. Achieving a high level of proficiency in a foreign language is impossible without fundamental language training in higher education. In most universities in the country, students master at least two foreign languages [4, 1].

Listening training is very relevant today because speech communication is impossible without listening. The concept of listening includes the process of perceiving and understanding spoken speech. Listening is an important aspect of learning English [2].

Modern effective methods of teaching listening skills include everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening is considered to be the most learned skill. Because a little more focus on learning is enhanced through simple and fun activities and ultimately leads to better results. In this case, it doesn't matter whether you work with small or large groups of students, as long as you use one of the following methods to develop yourself.

Unique ways to teach students to listen well:

Interpersonal activity

Interpersonal activities are one of the most effective ways to develop strong listening skills in students. We can add the following to this method:

1. Role playing
2. Mock interviews
3. Interpersonal dialogues
4. Storytelling and more

In this, students are divided into small groups of two or three, and they are asked questions according to the style.

For example, you can tell a student to interview for a job at a company or for an article in a newspaper. Storytelling activities can greatly develop students by giving them opportunities to ask questions.

Group activity. Large group activities also help students develop listening comprehension in interaction.

A simple group activity is also a good example of a useful way to teach students listening skills. For the first activity, students will be divided into groups of five or more and you should ask them to study one interest or at least two other hobbies. It is necessary to ask clarifying questions to the students. During the activity, you can allow it because it is useful.

The second part of the activity is to allow students to sit in large groups. For example, let them communicate about the name of the group member they met and their hobbies. Both of these activities lead to effective listening growth.

Audio segments. We can also teach students listening skills through audio segments such as:

1. radio programs
2. educational lectures
3. with online podcasts and other audio messages.

Interactive listening programs should be used with students in and after the classroom.

It is necessary to create conditions for them to perform the exercise independently. First of all, prepare the students to listen by giving instructions and imagining whatever you want to teach. It is up to each teacher to choose shorter or longer audio segments and more difficult or easier material for these types of exercises.

Teachers can use interesting messages to engage students. You can get them on radio or TV. It is also appropriate to use the computer to convey messages to them. Students do not need to understand all the words, but they must listen carefully to the messages and understand what the message is they should know about [2].

Video segments. Another very useful resource for teaching listening skills is video segments that:

1. brief sketches
2. documentaries
3. dramatic or comedic material
4. news programs
5. There may be interview segments.

As with the audio segment, the teacher can choose the part and length of the audio based on the level of their students, which they can do the same for the video segment.

One of the main conditions of this method is to watch it without any sound and discuss it together with the student. It improves students' listening and thinking skills.

Movies and TV shows. Movies are one of the art forms. Language learners are recommended to watch TV to increase their vocabulary and deepen their knowledge. Movies are one of the most used teaching methods, because in movies a wide range of vocabulary can be discovered [3].

In conclusion, it should be said that in this article, several methods and instructions were given for the development of listening comprehension skills. No matter which method you use to teach listening, there are a few basic guidelines to keep in mind. First, do not expect great results from the students at first, because even the most capable listener will never remember the message completely and clearly from the initial exercises. Secondly, it is very important to create questions for students not only clearly, but at the level of their abilities, so as not to make mistakes. Third, to help students find their direction and style.

If these rules are followed, students will learn listening comprehension better, because no matter what method they use, they will improve their listening comprehension skills.

Listening is a complex receptive mental-mimic activity associated with the perception, understanding and active processing of information contained in an oral speech message. Listening is carried out as a result of performing a number of complex logical operations, such as analysis, synthesis, deduction, induction, comparison, abstraction, concretization [3].

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